

Condensed Thiophene Derivatives, Part-I. Electrophilic Substitution in Benzo [b] Thiophanthrene.

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Electrophilic substitutions in benzo [b] thiophanthrene have been studied and orientations arrived at. During the work a number of thiophanthraquinones have been unambiguously synthesised.

In a programme on our studies on condensed thiophene derivatives, it became necessary to prepare derivatives of dibenzothiophene and its benzologues of unquestionable orientation. The course of electrophilic substitution in these compounds has not been studied and the present communication deals on the studies on acylation, chloromethylation and bromination of benzo [b] thiophanthrene (I).

The quinones (VI, VII, VIII) were prepared by standard methods. To illustrate, (VI) was synthesised from ethylbenzene by way of 5-ethyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (X) which was oxidised to 5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (XI) via the related anil⁷. On condensation with phenacyl bromide in alkali (XI) gave the keto-acid (XII) which on cyclisation by way of the acid chloride gave the quinone (VI). Alternatively, the dione (XI) on reaction with chloroacetic acid in alkali gave the dicarboxylic acid (XIII)¹. The related anhydride (ν_{max} 1770, 1838 cm^{-1}) on Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene gave 3-benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (XIV) which on cyclisation gave the same quinone (VI). The other quinones with different substituents (ethyl, methyl,

X

XI

XII

XIII

XIV

Friedel-Crafts acetylation of (I) gave a mono acetyl derivative ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1682 cm^{-1}) which on Wolff-Kishner reduction afforded an ethyl benzo [b] thiophanthrene. For the sake of identification 2-, 8-, and 9-ethyl-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinones (VI, VII, VIII) were unambiguously synthesised but the reduction of these quinones to the related thiophanthrenes by (a) zinc dust and ammonia¹, (b) copper-zinc couple and ammonia², (c) boiling hydriodic acid³ and (d) diborane⁴ gave either unchanged or interactable products. In the event, the ethyl benzo [b] thiophanthrene in question was oxidised with chromic acid¹ and the resulting product was, to our surprise, identified as the unsubstituted quinone (V) leaving the choice of orientation at either 6- or 11-position. Of these, position 6 is preferred as this is *ortho* to S. The compound is therefore 6-acetylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene (II). Subsequent studies on bromination, as set forth in the sequel, lead to the same conclusion. The result is in contrast to our earlier finding on the oxygen analogue (I, O in place of S) where we obtained a different result⁵. The difference in the electronegativity of the hetero atoms have shown the difference in orientation (+E effect = OR > SR > SeR)⁶.

bromine) at different positions were secured essentially by methods illustrated above or by employing minor modifications thereon.

Chloromethylation of (I) gave a mono chloromethyl derivative which on catalytic reduction afforded a methyl thiophanthrene as a light yellow viscous liquid. Here too the orientation was established at 6-position because on oxidation the quinone (V) was again obtained. Thus the chloromethyl compound is established as (III). During this work 2-, 8-,¹ and 9-methyl-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinones¹ were secured for comparison (*vide* experimental).

The bromination of (I) was very facile and the resulting dibromobenzo [b] thiophanthrene on oxidation gave a monobromo thiophanthraquinone identified as 8-bromo-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (IX)¹ by direct comparison. The dibromo compound is therefore identified as (IV). It is obvious that the initial substitution of bromine at position 6 has directed the entry of the second bromine atom at position 8 suppressing the influence of the hetero atom S (XV,

arrows). It is pertinent to point out if the initial entry of the bromine atom were at position 11, then position 9 would be activated (XVI, arrows). No 2- or 9-bromothiophanthraquinones could be detected, however, in the residue left in the purification of (IX).

Experimental

All m.ps. or b.ps. are uncorrected. Unless otherwise mentioned, the i. r. spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237 in KBr discs.

Acetylation of Benzo [b] thiophanthrene: A solution of aluminium chloride (1.08 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (10.0 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred ice cold (0-2°) mixture of benzo [b] thiophanthrene (1.0 g.), acetyl chloride (0.4 ml.) and tetrachloroethane (10.0 ml.) over a period of 20 min. The temperature was maintained at 0-2° for further 20 min. with constant shaking. On keeping the reaction mixture in a refrigerator for 48 hrs., an orange complex gradually separated which was decomposed with crushed ice-hydrochloric acid (5N). The solvents were removed by steam distillation. A light yellow mass, which separated, was taken up in benzene, washed, dried and finally chromatographed on an activated alumina column. Five fractions were collected with benzene as an eluent. The second to fifth fractions gave pure 6-acetylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene (II; 0.6 g.). The ketone crystallised from benzene in short yellowish needles, m.p. 91-93°. (Found: C, 78.30; H, 4.41. $C_{15}H_{12}OS$ requires: C, 78.25; H, 4.38%). i.r. spectrum $\nu_{C=O}$ 1682 cm^{-1} , ν_{C-S} 704 cm^{-1} .

The oxime crystallised from MeOH in light yellow crystals, m.p. 149-50°. (Found: C, 74.12; H, 4.68; N, 4.79. $C_{15}H_{12}NOS$ requires: C, 74.21; H, 4.50; N, 4.81%).

Wolff-Kishner Reduction of 6-Acetylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene: The above acetyl compound (1.0 g.) in dry diethylene glycol (10.0 ml.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (2.0 ml.; 99-100%) and boiled for 2 hrs. On cooling, the colourless hydrazone separated out. To this, pot. hydroxide (2.0 g.) was added after removing water from the system by distillation and heated to 190-200° for 3 hrs till evolution of nitrogen ceased. The mixture was cooled to r.t. and diluted with water and the oily layer extracted with ether, washed, dried and distilled under reduced pressure at 140-50°/1 mm. to give a light yellowish liquid, 6-ethylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene (0.8 g.). (Found: C, 82.39; H, 5.36. $C_{15}H_{14}S$ requires: C, 82.42; H, 5.38%).

The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex was crystallised from benzene in orange-red crystalline mass, m.p. 192-93°. (Found: N, 7.26. $C_{18}H_{14}S.C_{13}H_8N_3O_7$ requires: N, 7.28%).

Oxidation of 6-ethylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene: A solution of 6-ethylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene (0.53 g.) in a minimum volume of AcOH (3.0 ml.) was treated with a solution of chromic acid (0.55 g.) in a minimum volume of water, boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ min. The colour of the solution changed to yellowish-green. After cooling and diluting with water, a yellow quinone separated out on scratching. This was extracted with benzene, dried over $MgSO_4$ and chromatographed on an activated alumina column in benzene. Yellow needles of 6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (V; 0.1 g.) were obtained on concentration and subsequent crystallisation from AcOH. It was identified by m.p., mixed m.p. (212-13°; no depression) and i.r. spectrum. (Found: C, 72.81; H, 3.08. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_2S$: C, 72.73; H, 3.05%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-quinone absorption at 1665 cm^{-1} , and ν_{C-S} band at 702 cm^{-1} .

Bromination of Benzo [b] thiophanthrene: A solution of bromine (0.4 ml.) in AcOH (2.0 ml.) was added dropwise to a solution of benzo [b] thiophanthrene (1.17g.) in AcOH (10.0 ml.) over a period of 20 min with constant stirring. The mixture was kept at r.t. for 6 hrs. 6,8-Dibromobenzo [b] thiophanthrene, which was separated out, was collected, washed with EtOH and crystallised from AcOH in colourless plates, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 48.89; H, 2.16. $C_{15}H_8Br_2S$ requires: C, 48.99; H, 2.06%).

Oxidation of 6,8-Dibromobenzo [b] thiophanthrene: Chromic acid (0.5 g.) dissolved in minimum volume of water (3 drops) was added to 6,8-dibromobenzo [b] thiophanthrene (0.8 g.) also dissolved in minimum volume of AcOH (9.0 ml.). The mixture was gently boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ min. and diluted with water to give 8-bromo-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (IX), which was purified by chromatography over an alumina column. 8-Bromoquinone crystallised from AcOH in silky yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 219-20°. On treatment with conc. sulphuric acid a dark violet colour was obtained. (Found: C, 55.82; H, 2.07. $C_{15}H_7BrO_2S$ requires: C, 55.98; H, 2.04%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-quinone absorption at 1660 cm^{-1} and ν_{C-S} band at 700 cm^{-1} .

Identification of this quinone was confirmed by m.p. and mixed m.ps. and comparison of i.r. spectrum with an authentic sample.

Reductive Acetylation of 8-Bromo-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone: A mixture of foregoing bromo-quinone (0.1 g.), zinc-dust (0.08 g.), acetic anhydride (3.2 ml.) and fused sod acetate (0.32 g.) was refluxed for 3 hrs. The colourless solution was poured into water and the residual zinc extracted with small quantities of AcOH. 8-Bromobenzo [b] thiophanthrene-6, 11-diacetate was collected and crystallised from AcOH in elongated colourless needles (0.07 g.), m.p. 207-08°. (Found: C, 55.88; H, 3.02. $C_{20}H_{13}BrO_4S$ requires: C, 55.94; H, 3.03%.)

Chloromethylation of Benzo [b] thiophanthrene: A rapid stream of dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed into a vigorously stirred mixture of benzo [b] thiophanthrene (2.0 g.) and aqueous formaldehyde solution (6.0 ml.; 40%) till the mixture was saturated. During this period, temperature of the mixture raised to 60-65°. This temp. was maintained for 1½ hrs. while a slow stream of dry hydrogen chloride gas was continuously passed into the mixture which was cooled and diluted with water, the viscous mass was extracted with ether and washed successively with water, sod. bicarbonate solution (10%) and water. After drying over $MgSO_4$ and removal of solvent, a yellowish material was obtained. 6-Chloromethylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene crystallised from EtOH in cream colour plates (2.4 g.), m.p. 182-83°. (Found: C, 72.09; H, 3.91. $C_{17}H_{11}ClS$ requires: C, 72.21; H, 3.89%.)

Catalytic Reduction of 6-Chloromethylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene: 6-Chloromethyl derivative (2.0 g.) was catalytically hydrogenated at the r.t. and ordinary pressure in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.5 g.; 30%) in ethyl acetate (20.0 ml.) containing potassium hydroxide (0.1 g.) in water (1.0 ml.). Hydrogenation was complete with the absorption of one mole hydrogen over a period of 4-5 hrs. The solvent was removed and the residual oil distilled at 200-240°/2 mm. to give 6-methylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene (1.1 g.) as a liquid, which did not solidify on keeping in a refrigerator even for a long time. (Found: C, 82.16; H, 4.98. $C_{17}H_{12}S$ requires: C, 82.24; H, 4.87%.)

Oxidation of 6-methylbenzo [b] thiophanthrene: The above thiohydrocarbon (0.52 g.) was dissolved in minimum volume of glacial AcOH (2.0 ml.) and added to a solution of chromic acid (.55 g.) in water (4 drops) and boiled for 1½ min. On work up a yellow solid separated (0.1 g.) which was identified as 6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone, m.p. 212-13°, (identical i.r. spectra). (Found: C, 72.76; H, 3.12. Calc. for $C_{16}H_8O_2S$: C, 72.73; H, 3.05%.)

5-Ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (XI): A solution of oxalyl chloride (6.0 ml.) in dry ether (15.0 ml.) was added dropwise to a well-cooled solution of 4-ethylthiophenol⁹ (6.9 g.) in dry ether (40.0 ml.) and kept at r.t. till the initial evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased.

It was then refluxed for 1 hr. The excess of oxalyl chloride was removed by treating thrice with dry ether and their subsequent removal under reduced pressure. The residual oil was taken up in carbon disulphide (40.0 ml.) and then anhydrous aluminium chloride (15.0 g.) was added in small portions over a period of 1 hr. at 0°; after leaving it for 3 hrs. at r.t. the mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. The dione crystallised from AcOH, m.p. 110-11°; yield 90%. (Found: C, 62.48; H, 4.22. $C_{10}H_8O_2S$ requires: C, 62.50; H, 4.20%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-quinone absorption at 1715 cm^{-1} , ν_{C-S} band at 799 cm^{-1} .

5-Methylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione: was prepared according to the method described by Papa, Schwenk and Ginsberg⁹.

5-Bromobenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione: 5-Bromobenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione was prepared following the method of Harley-Mason and Mann⁸. For this 3-hydroxy-5-bromobenzo [b] thiophene¹⁰ (5-bromothioindoxyl; 5.0 g.) was dissolved in boiling NaOH solution (50.0 ml.; 5%), cooled down to 60°. To this was added, with stirring, a solution of *p*-nitroso-dimethylaniline (5.0 g.) in dilute hydrochloric acid (30.0 ml.; 5%), keeping the temp. at 60°. The violet *anil* separated rapidly on cooling. After leaving for 12 hrs., the *anil* was collected and thoroughly washed successively with cold water, dilute hydrochloric acid (2*N*), hot and cold water and dried; yield 5.0 g. The *anil* was boiled with hydrochloric acid (100.0 ml.; 15%) for 4 hrs and filtered after cooling. The undissolved residue was washed with water and digested with an excess of boiling sod. carbonate solution (50%) for 30 min. The hot mixture was filtered into crushed ice and then acidified to give 5-bromobenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (4.1 g) which was collected, washed with water and crystallised from MeOH in reddish-brown needles, m.p. 177-78°. (Found: C, 39.57; H, 1.33. $C_8H_3BrO_2S$ requires: C, 39.51; H, 1.23%.)

2-Benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic Acid (XII): Ethanol was added to a mixture of 5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (2.0 g.), phenacyl bromide (4.0 g.) and NaOH solution (25.0 ml.; 2*N*) till all went into solution. The mixture was then refluxed for 7-8 hrs., cooled, filtered, solvent removed and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid to give 2-benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic acid (2.2 g.), m.p. 115-17°. The compound gave an orange-red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 69.65; H, 4.57. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3S$ requires: C, 69.67; H, 4.55%). i.r. Spectrum: Aryl ketone absorption at 1668 cm^{-1} , carboxylic acid at 1688 cm^{-1} , ν_{C-S} at 690 cm^{-1} .

The synthesis of the following keto-acids was effected by an unambiguous route as described above.

2-Benzoyl-5-bromobenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic Acid crystallised from AcOH in colourless needles, m.p. 220-21°, giving an orange colour with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 53.20; H, 2.51. $C_{16}H_8BrO_3S$ requires: C, 53.19; H, 2.49%.)

2-Benzoyl-5-methylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic Acid: crystallised from AcOH in short colourless needles, m.p. 234-35°. It gave an orange colouration with conc. sulphuric acid (Found: C, 68.88; H, 4.09. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3S$ requires: C, 68.91; H, 4.08%).

2-Ethyl-6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (VI): 2-Benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic acid (0.5 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by dissolving in thiophene-free benzene (10.0 ml.) and adding thionyl chloride (0.25 ml.) followed by catalytic amount of dry pyridine. A clear solution was obtained after refluxing for 3 hrs. After removing benzene and excess of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure, carbon disulphide (15.0 ml.) was added to the brown oily mass, cooled down to 0° and aluminium chloride (1.5 g.) was added slowly. The quinone crystallised from AcOH in yellow needles (0.21 g.), m. p. 156-57°. The compound imparted a dark violet colour to conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 73.94; H, 4.19. $C_{18}H_{12}O_2S$ requires: C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-Quinone absorption at 1655 cm^{-1} and ν_{C-S} band at 700 cm^{-1} . The most obvious route to 2-bromo- and 2-methyl quinones is by an adaptation of methods as used above.

2-Bromo-6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (IX): crystallised in fine yellow needles, m. p. 222-23°, imparting a violet colouration on treatment with conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 55.99; H, 2.11. $C_{16}H_7BrO_2S$ requires: C, 55.98; H, 2.04%).

2-Methyl-6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone: crystallised in silky yellow needles, m. p. 188°, giving a violet colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 73.48; H, 3.82. $C_{17}H_{10}O_2S$ requires: C, 73.38; H, 3.62%).

3-Benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic Acid (XIV): 5-Ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (1.47 g.) was dissolved in sod. carbonate solution (30.0 ml.; 2N) and heated on water-bath at 50-60°; a solution of chloroacetic acid (0.68 g.) neutralised with sod. carbonate solution (10%) was added slowly and the mixture heated on water-bath at 70-75° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. It was cooled down and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid; the 4-ethyl-2-glyoxylic-phenylthioglycolic acid which precipitated out, was filtered. The reddish crystalline mass was crystallised from benzene in colourless needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 144-46°. (Found: C, 53.75; H, 4.61. $C_{13}H_{12}O_6S$ requires: C, 53.73; H, 4.51%). This thioglycolic acid (0.9 g.) was cyclised by fusing with NaOH (15.0 ml.; 100%) on an oil-bath at 200° for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. till the yellow colour turned practically colourless. The mass was collected, dissolved in water and 5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid (XIII; 0.7 g.) was obtained on acidification with conc. hydrochloric acid. It was crystallised from a large volume of hot water in pale yellow elongated needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 194-96°. (Found: C, 53.67; H, 5.05. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4S.H_2O$ requires: C, 53.73; H, 4.51%). The foregoing dicarboxylic acid (0.6 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (4.0 ml.) and refluxed for 2 $\frac{1}{2}$ hrs. The anhydride was removed by

distillation under reduced pressure. On cooling, fine light yellow needles of 5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride (0.55 g.) were obtained, m.p. 130-31°. (Found: C, 62.12; H, 3.51. $C_{13}H_8O_5S$ requires: C, 62.07; H, 3.47%). i. r. Spectrum: Anhydride absorption at 1770 cm^{-1} . The above anhydride (0.55 g.) was dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (10.0 ml.) and cooled down to 0°, then aluminium chloride (2.0 g.) was added to it in parts over a period of 15 min. and left overnight. Next day, it was boiled for 1 hr., cooled and decomposed with crushed ice-hydrochloric acid (5N). 3-Benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic acid (XIV; 0.2 g.) crystallised from AcOH in colourless needles, m.p. 158-60°. (Found: C, 69.59; H, 4.56. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3S$ requires: C, 69.67; H, 4.55%). i. r. Spectrum: Aryl ketone absorption at 1665 cm^{-1} , carboxyl carbonyl at 1680 cm^{-1} & ν_{C-S} band at 650 cm^{-1} .

The following compounds were also obtained using the above described procedure.

4-Methyl-2-glyoxylic-phenylthioglycolic Acid crystallised in light yellow crystals, m.p. above 300°; (Found: C, 51.81; H, 4.11. $C_{11}H_{10}O_6S$ requires: C, 51.97; H, 3.97%).

5-Methylbenzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic Acid crystallised in pale yellow needles, m.p. 246-47° (decomp.). (Found: C, 51.86; H, 3.85. $C_{11}H_8O_4S.H_2O$ requires: C, 51.97; H, 3.97%).

5-Methylbenzo [b] thiophene-2, 3-dicarboxylic Anhydride crystallised in fine light silky yellow needles, m. p. 208-10°. (Found: C, 60.43; H, 2.61. $C_{11}H_6O_5S$ requires: C, 60.56; H, 2.77%).

3-Benzoyl-5-methylbenzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic Acid crystallised in colourless needles, m.p. 202-03°. On treatment with conc. sulphuric acid it gave an orange colour. (Found: C, 68.81; H, 4.12. $C_{17}H_{12}O_3S$ requires: C, 68.91; H, 4.08%).

2-Ethyl-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (VI): 3-Benzoyl-5-ethylbenzo [b] thiophene-2, carboxylic acid (1.0 g.) was dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (10.0 ml.) and thionyl chloride (0.5 ml.) was added at r. t. followed by one drop of pyridine. After leaving for 15 min., it was refluxed for 3 hrs. on the water-bath. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The brown oily mass was taken up in dry carbon disulphide (25.0 ml.) and cooled to 0° and powdered aluminium chloride (2.5 g.) was added and the whole mass was kept overnight at the r.t. The quinone (VI) crystallised in yellow needles (0.65 g.), m.p. 156-58°, identical with the quinone prepared by the previous method (Found: C, 73.88; H, 4.23. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{12}O_2S$: C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). By similar method, 2-Methyl-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (m.p. 188-89°) was also prepared from 3-benzoyl-5-methylbenzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic acid. (Found: C, 73.58; H, 3.74. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{10}O_2S$: C, 73.48; H, 3.62%).

3-(4'-Ethylbenzoyl) benzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic Acid: Benzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dicarboxylic anhydride⁴ (2.04 g.) was taken up in freshly distilled ethylbenzene (15.0 ml.) and cooled down to 0°; then anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.0 g.) was added to it in small portions over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was kept overnight in a refrigerator, when an orange coloured aluminium-complex gradually formed which was decomposed with hydrochloric acid (5*N*). The acid crystallised from AcOH in short colourless needles, m.p. 199-200° giving an orange colouration to sulphuric acid, yield 1.21 g. (Found: C, 61.63; H, 4.65. C₁₈H₁₄O₃S requires: C, 69.67; H, 4.55%). i.r. Spectrum: Aryl ketone absorption at 1668 cm⁻¹ & carboxyl carbonyl at 1688 cm⁻¹.

8-Ethyl-6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (VII): *3-(4'-Ethylbenzoyl) benzo [b] thiophene-2-carboxylic acid* (1.56 g.) was dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (15.0 ml.) and thionyl chloride (0.5 ml.) was added to it followed by one drop of dry pyridine. It was refluxed for 3 hrs. till a clear solution was obtained. After removing last traces of thionyl chloride under reduced pressure, the brown liquid was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (15.0 ml.). Powdered aluminium chloride (5.0 g.) was added to it in portions and the resulting reaction mixture was kept overnight at r.t. The quinone crystallised from AcOH in short yellow needles (1.0 g.), m.p. 138-39°. It gave a dark violet colouration to sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 74.01; H, 4.23. C₁₈H₁₂O₂S requires: C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-Quinone absorption at 1622 cm⁻¹.

2-(4'-Ethylbenzoyl) benzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic Acid: A mixture of aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide solution of benzo [b] thiophene-2,3-dione (3.4 g.) and 4-ethylphenacyl bromide (4.6 g.) was refluxed for 3 hrs. and cooled. Ethanol was boiled off and the residue filtered and acidified to give the desired *keto-acid*, which was crystallised from AcOH in short needles, m.p. 223-24°, yield 5.25 g. It imparted an orange colour to conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 69.52; H, 4.81. C₁₈H₁₄O₃S requires: C, 69.67; H, 4.55%).

2-(4'-Bromobenzoyl) benzo [b] thiophene-3-carboxylic Acid crystallised in shining short needles, m.p.

230-31°. An orange colouration was obtained on treatment with conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 53.12; H, 2.52. C₁₆H₉BrO₃S requires: C, 53.19; H, 2.49%).

9-Ethyl-6,11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone (VIII): The foregoing *keto-acid* (0.5 g.) was converted into its acid chloride by dissolving it in thiophene-free benzene (10.0 ml.) and adding thionyl chloride (0.25 ml.) followed by catalytic amount of dry pyridine. A clear solution was obtained after refluxing for 3 hrs. and cyclised as before with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 g.). The quinone crystallised from AcOH in beautiful yellow needles, yield 0.21 g., m.p. 166-67°, giving a reddish-violet colouration to conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 73.91; H, 4.21. C₁₈H₁₂O₂S requires: C, 73.96; H, 4.14%). i.r. Spectrum: 1,4-Quinone absorption at 1657 cm⁻¹, *ν*_{C-S} band at 690 cm⁻¹.

9-Bromo-6, 11-benzo [b] thiophanthraquinone crystallised in beautiful silky yellow needles, m.p. 246-47°, was also synthesised following the above method. It gave a dark violet colouration to conc. sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 55.83; H, 2.11. C₁₆H₇BrO₂S requires: C, 55.98; H, 2.04%).

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